

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
Religious Education Department (RED)
School of Teacher Education and Humanities
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PROJECT PROPOSAL

I. Project Title

"Gaudete et Exsultate II"

A Comparative Exploration of Basic Education and Tertiary Employees' Spiritual Intelligence and Work Morale: Basis In Crafting Institutional Project-based Activities

II. Abstract

The proposed study is a second phase research on the state of work morale and the level of spiritual intelligence of the SMU employees, both teaching and non-teaching, of the Basic Education Department which includes the Elementary Department, Junior High School, and Senior High School.

Based on the results and finding of the first phase of this study that focused on the WM and SI of the employees of the College Department, it is highly recommended that a study should also be conducted at the Basic Education Level. Based on the recommendations, a study must be conducted among the employees of the basic education departments as they may differ in some aspects like spiritual intelligence and work circumstances or perceptions in the personal, relational and spiritual dimensions with the college employees. In so doing, the claims on the importance of SI and WM in school environment will be strongly established and as such, there will be a more holistic analysis of the state of the employees in SMU in terms of their workplace values and work efficiency. This will also provide a stronger claim for policy recommendations and crafting of project-based institutional activities which may be developed into institutional programs with the aim of boosting the work morale of employees through job satisfaction and enhanced spiritual intelligence in the personal, relational, and spiritual dimensions.

Thus, this study embarks on a quantitative-qualitative, descriptive-comparative and correlational research design in determining the level of spiritual intelligence (SI) vis-à-vis the level of work morale (WM) of **all basic education employees, both teaching and non-teaching personnel** of St. Mary's University (SMU). It will utilize researcher-modified and contextualized tools based on standardized survey questionnaire in determining the spiritual intelligence and survey questionnaire on the level of work morale. The results of the survey will serve as an initial basis in analyzing the state of the work morale and spiritual intelligence of the employees. Based on the results, the researchers will try to see the role, connection, implication, or effects of spiritual intelligence in the work morale of employees in the basic education level. The analysis of the results will be used as basis for relevant policy recommendations to further strengthen their spiritual intelligence and work morale. It can also serve as a basis for recommendation in crafting a module for proposed activities like prayerful encounter, faith and fellowship, and praise and worship in the context of *Lectio Divina*, in order to help and inspire employees to concretely realize their missional call to holiness inspired by *Gaudete et Exsultate*. Eventually, the end result of this study is to have a basis for relevant basic education level policy recommendation to enhance SI and to boost WM.

Key Words: Spiritual intelligence, Spiritual Intelligence (SI), Spiritual Quotient (SQ), Work Morale, Holiness, Spiritual Wellness, Workplace Spiritual intelligence,

III. Research Agenda/ Theme Reflective of the Paper: Call to holiness, Spiritual Wellness, Healthy Work Morale (accountability, healthy disposition in the workplace, job satisfaction)

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V. Mechanism Applied for: MECHANISM D

VI. Rationale

Today, many, if not all Catholic schools, are worried about the “exodus” of teachers to public high schools, basic educations, and universities primarily because of the search for “greener pasture.” Many teachers opt to go to government educational institutions because of the promise of high salaries and other opportunities for economic security. Adding to the problem of Catholic schools is the influx of students in the public schools because of the free tuition fees and subsidies offered to them. It goes without saying that fewer students imply less financial viability. And teachers in effect suffer or may cause financial instability because of the continuously escalating prices of commodities. In short, Catholic schools inevitably face this exigent issue, and it needs a serious and immediate response to this crisis.

Simply put, are employees of Catholic educational institutions remain happy, fulfilled, and stable in their work morale? Are they not faltering in their commitment because of the strong temptations to depart in search of a possibly more promising work or a more lucrative career? Do they still find meaning in their current workplaces? More importantly, do they still find the mission of Catholic education relevant? In these trying times in Catholic institutions, there is a need to revisit employees in their workplaces.

The recent conference of the Catholic Educational Association of the Philippines (CEAP) and the Philippine Conference on New Evangelization (PCNE) held at the Pontifical and Royal University of Santo Tomas - Manila last July 18-22, 2018 enthemed, “Moved with Compassion... Feed the Multitude” emphasized the mission of Jesus as the same mission every baptized Catholic – that is, to respond to the “signs of the times” that continue to challenge the Christian faith. Every Christian is reminded of their commitment to share in the servanthood of Jesus, especially to the vulnerable young people of this generation who are often the common victims of secularism, a world that is becoming immensely materialistic, commodified, and totally detached from the religious and the spiritual.

Similarly, the Apostolic exhortation of Pope Francis, *Gaudete et Exsultate* (GE) (Rejoice and be Glad!) focuses on the call to holiness of every Christian. In Article 14, he says,

To be holy does not require being a bishop, a priest or a religious... We are all called to be holy by living our lives with love and by bearing witness in everything we do, wherever we find ourselves... Are you married? Be holy by loving and caring for your husband or wife, as Christ does for the Church. Do you work for a living? Be holy by laboring with integrity and skill in the service of your brothers and sisters... Are you in a position of authority? Be holy by working for the common good and renouncing personal gain.

The exhortation challenges every Christian to reflect deeply in today’s challenging times. In GE art. 17, Pope Francis that at times life presents great challenges. However, through these challenges, “the Lord calls us anew to a conversion that can make his grace more evident in our lives, ‘in order that we may share his holiness’ (Heb 12:10).” In fact, “a Christian cannot think of his or her mission on earth without seeing it as a path of holiness, for “this is the will of God, your sanctification” (1 Thess 4:3).” (GE, 19). He further urges all Christians “to realize what that word is, the message of Jesus that God wants to speak to the world by your life. Let yourself be transformed. Let yourself be renewed by the Spirit, so that this can happen, lest you fail in your precious mission (GE, 24).

Several exhortations of Pope Francis focused on the value of spiritual intelligence. In the previous exhortations, he challenges all Christians, both the clergy and the lay faithful to show their commitment in such a way that everything they do has evangelical meaning and identifies them all the more with Jesus Christ. For instance, he emphasizes on the spiritual intelligence of the catechist, the spiritual intelligence of priesthood, and the spiritual intelligence of work. We see these spiritual intelligence

exhortations , in *Evangelii Gaudium* that speaks of a spiritual intelligence of mission, in *Laudato Si'* an ecological spiritual intelligence, and in *Amoris Laetitia* on a spiritual intelligence of family life. Thus, spiritual intelligence matters most in the lives of all Christians.

It is in this regard that this research project finds a challenge to analyze, interpret, and move into action regarding the spiritual wellness and work morale among professionals specifically in a Catholic educational Institution. With the modern thinking, feeling, acting, and valuing of people, specifically multi-sectoral professionals, spiritual intelligence could complete the multi-dimensional character of human complex behaviors in various workplaces.

The proposed study is a second phase research on the state of work morale and the level of spiritual intelligence of the SMU employees, both teaching and non-teaching, of the Basic Education Department which includes the Elementary Department, Junior High School, and Senior High School. This proposed study believes that there is a connection between spiritual intelligence and a successful and satisfying professionalism specifically on work morale. In other words, spiritual intelligence and high productivity in an organization are interrelated. This suggests that spiritual intelligence is strongly related to the well being of individuals, organizations, and societies in the workplace.

Based on the results and finding of the first phase of this study that focused on the WM and SI of the employees of the College Department, it is highly recommended that a study should also be conducted at the Basic Education Level. Based on the recommendations, a study must be conducted among the employees of the basic education departments as they may differ in some aspects like spiritual intelligence and work circumstances or perceptions in the personal, relational and spiritual dimensions with the college employees. In so doing, the claims on the importance of SI and WM in school environment will be strongly established and as such, there will be a more holistic analysis of the state of the employees in SMU in terms of their workplace values and work efficiency. This will also provide a stronger claim in crafting project-based institutional activities which may eventually be developed into institutional programs with the aim of boosting the work morale of employees through job satisfaction and enhanced spiritual intelligence in the personal, relational, and spiritual dimensions.

The institutional programs and activities of SMU cater to all departments of the institution. In fact, the mission-vision of the school involves the whole institution. In other words, the Marian culture or "branding" of the institution, and thus the formation of prospective professionals commences in the basic education. In short, all programs of the institution are geared toward the whole Marian community, - students, employees, and other stakeholders. Therefore, since this developmental study aims to design institutional activities that could possibly enhance the SI and WM of all employees, it is deemed necessary that the status of the SI and MW of all departments must be given equal attention and priority., thus, the need to determine the job satisfaction of the employees of the basic education in relation to their work morale and spiritual intelligence.

Hence, this study on spiritual intelligence and work morale focuses on the SI and WM of basic education employees, both teaching and non-teaching personnel. The results of this study will serve as a basis for in crafting project-based institutional activities that are primarily intended to enhance SI and to boost the WM of SMU basic education employees and the college department as a whole. This second phase of the study shall mainly focus on the basic education department. However, the results of this study shall be correlated with the results of the first phase which focused on the college department. The researchers believe that nature of work and every workplace may differ in several aspects. Thus, the basic education departments, namely the grade school, junior high school, and senior high school necessitate a separate study. However, the results of this study, in one way or the other, are deemed necessary and contributory in crafting holistic project-based institutional activities that aim to enhance SI and WM for a greater satisfaction at SMU.

VII. Statement of Purpose/Objectives

Bearing in mind the value of professionalism and the significance of spiritual intelligence among employees in a Catholic educational institution as well as the importance of productivity through a positive work morale, the general objectives or purposes of the proposed research are the following:

1. To determine the level SI and the level of WM of SMU Basic Education employees, both teaching and non-teaching personnel to establish a baseline data on their SI and WM.
 2. To determine significant correlation between SI and work morale of the basic education employees.
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3. To compare the level of SI and the level of work morale of employees when grouped according to the following profile variables:
 - a. Departments (Basic Education and College Departments)
 - b. Years of Service
 - c. Work Assignment (teaching and non teaching)
 - d. Sex
4. To craft or design project-based institutional activities to boost the employees' SI and work morale.

VIII. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework starts by identifying the profile of the respondents which includes biological sex; actual number of years in service; departments, and work assignment as to teaching and non-teaching. The profiles of the respondents are deemed significant in the assessment of their SI and work morale specifically in their considerably extensive experiences in the university.

After identifying the profile of the respondents, a researcher modified and contextualized survey tool will be used to measure the level of SI and the level of work morale of the respondents. The questionnaires will be reinforced by open-ended questions in order to come up with a more extensive analysis of the statistical data.

The result of the survey will be analyzed regarding the relevance, role, and connection of the level of SI and the level of work morale of the basic education employees and comparisons shall be made regarding the SI and WM based on the profile variables. The analysis will be seen in the light the Apostolic Exhortation of Pope Francis on the call to holiness, *Gaudete et Exsultate* (lit., Rejoice and be glad!) that primarily focuses on spiritual intelligence.

Eventually, the end-goal of this study is to establish a basis in crafting Project-based institutional activities to boost SI and WM of SMU Employees

The study of Carvajal (2013) on the work spiritual intelligence of high performing teachers and a similar study he conducted among selected government employees (2011) stresses that the development of spiritual intelligence leads to the development of spiritual capital that fundamentally reflects what an individual or an organization exists for, believes in, aspires to, and takes responsibility for. Thus, SI can play a significant role in the work place.

Covey (2004) also emphasizes that spiritual intelligence is a key component of leadership and effectiveness when he observed that "spiritual intelligence is the central and most fundamental of all the intelligences, because it becomes the source of guidance, and in this case, the workplace.

Therefore, the survey conducted by several institutions and agencies, like in several types of businesses (e.g., commercial business) and even among health care institutions, like hospitals, believe that spiritual intelligence or work spiritual intelligence matters in the work morale of employees.

IX. Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The primary goal of this stage of the study is to try to determine the level of spiritual intelligence and the level of work morale of basic education employees, both teaching and non-teaching personnel using standardized tools. The results of the survey will be the primary sources of data which will be

reinforced by open-ended questions wherein the answers shall be transcribed in verbatim. The analysis of data also includes specific articles of *Gaudete et Exsultate*, the call to Holiness, which will serve as grounding or foundation in the thrust of improving the SI and inspiring a healthy or positive work morale of employees in view of the call to holiness, that is the significance of spiritual intelligence in the Christian faith.

X. Significance of the Study

With the current challenges of the times, this study is deemed significant to the following:

1. to the basic education school administrators of SMU, to have an empirical data through a scientific study regarding the level of spiritual intelligence, and the level of work morale of basic education employees in today's trying times of Catholic educational institutions as basis for relevant policy making or programs for basic education employees on matters spiritual intelligence and work morale.
2. to basic education employees to be informed of their level of SI as well as the state of their work morale in the midst of different challenging instances and tempting offers outside their current workplaces and professional careers.
3. to students and stakeholders who are also the immediate beneficiaries of the healthy spiritual and positive work morale and dispositions of employees. Employees with such dispositions are probably more capable of delivering better services and develop more meaningful relationships to people.
4. to the office the Vice-President for Mission and Identity, especially the Center for Christian Formation (CCF) particularly Christian Faith Education Department (CFED) and Campus Ministry (CN), as well as the Faculty, Employees and Retirees Association and the SMU Union for their information about the state of spiritual intelligence and work morale of employees in view of planning, designing, and crafting activities or programs for the spiritual formation and in helping boost the work morale of employees.
5. To future researchers and especially those who continue to develop and establish the importance of spiritual intelligence as a scientific endeavor in trying to search for a more comprehensive way of measuring and understanding human intelligences.
6. To all Christian, especially Catholic Christians who relentlessly continue to find the meaning human existence regardless of the exigencies of the times and who believe that everyone, by virtue of baptism, is called to holiness.
7. to the CICM-Philippine Province for their future plans and actions in their continuing thrust of forming a CICM "branding" in their evangelization in communities and educational institutions.

XI. Definition of Terms

In this study, the following key terms and concepts, operationally and conceptually or theoretically defined, are deemed significant in course this study:

Basic Education Employees refer to the academic and non-academic employees of the SMU Grade School, Junior High School and Senior High School Department

"Call to Holiness" refers to the main theme of the Apostolic Exhortation of Pope Francis' *Gaudete et Exsultate* (Rejoice and be Glad) calling and challenging all Christians to spiritual faith conversion in all types of vocation and work.

Level of Spiritual Intelligence refers to the statistically computed average (mean) of the respondents based on a standardized and contextualized survey questionnaire. It can also refer to spiritual quotient (SQ).

Level of Work Morale refers to the statistically computed average (mean) of the respondents based on a survey questionnaire that generally describes work disposition, positivity and job satisfaction, among others.

Project-based institutional activities refer to well-designed actions or endeavors that are anchored or complementary with existing institutional programs (e.g. SMU Integral Growth and Lifestyle Advocacy (SIGLA), GAWAD MARIA, spiritual recollection for employees, among others) that could

possibly boost the SI and WM of employees. Eventually, project-based activities could serve as basis in designing new programs that would respond to the call of the times.

Spiritual intelligence refers to the process of seeking personal authenticity, genuineness, and wholeness; transcending one's current locus of centrality (i.e., recognizing concerns beyond oneself); developing a greater connectedness to self and others through relationships and community; deriving meaning, purpose, and direction in life; and openness to exploring a relationship with a higher power or powers that transcend human existence and human knowing. (Bryant, 2007). **Spiritual Intelligence** (SI) refers to the ability to access higher meanings, values, abiding purposes, and unconscious aspects of the self and to embed these meanings, values, and purposes in living a richer and more creative life (Zohar and Marshall (2005).

Spiritual Quotient (SQ) refers to the computed average of spiritual intelligence based on a standardized test. Sometimes it is interchangeably used with spiritual intelligence in the parlance of multiple intelligences (e.g., IQ, EQ, etc.)

Work morale refers to the positive and healthy disposition of employees which describes their overall outlook, attitude, satisfaction, and confidence they feel at work in their specific workplaces or work environment.

XII. Review of Related Literature

This study considers the following works, concepts, and ideas from different sources helpful in the analysis and expositions as well as in guiding the researchers achieve their objectives:

A. On Spiritual Intelligence, Work Spirituality, and Teacher Education

According to Palmer (2003), there is a connection between spirituality and a successful and satisfying teaching. He strongly believes that there is a "spiritual" element to good teaching. Thus, spiritual intelligence has a place in teacher education. Spirituality according to Palmer is the eternal human yearning connected with something larger than our own ego or the diverse ways to answer the heart's longing to be connected with the largeness of life. He would simply mean that good teaching cannot be reduced to techniques but is rooted in the identity and integrity of the teacher. This expounds that good teaching takes myriad forms but good teachers share one trait and that is the "capacity for connectedness." This ability to make connections is known as the work spirituality or the spirituality at work.

Palmer (2011) added that to educate is to guide students on an inner journey toward more truthful ways of seeing and being in the world. Gotz (2011) supports that spirituality developed in the context of a teaching life would have to strive not only to maintain an ongoing openness toward new and diverse ways of letting people learn, but also toward letting oneself learn how to let other learn, in such a way that one would progressively become transparent to what one intends to let others learn, so that in "seeing" the teacher they would learn the taught. Kumar (2011) considers this as the attitude to change and transform according to environment which will result in increasing one's productivity and effectiveness at the workplace.

Work spirituality and high productivity in an organization are intimately intertwined or interrelated. Cunha, Rego & D'Oliviera (2011) believes that every theory of organization is a theory of organizational spirituality. From their findings, they suggest that there may be both a meaningful and an instrumental side in the relationship between organizations and spirituality.

According to Sheep (2011), workplace spirituality has potentially strong relevance to the well being of individuals, organizations, and societies. This idea is supported by Tacey (2004) who underscored that we are now in the spirituality revolution, describing it as a spontaneous movement in society and a significant new interest in the reality of spirit and its healing effects on life, health, community and well-being. According to Carvajal (2013) Tacey recognizes that we have outgrown the ideals and values of previous times and reveals an image of the spiritual situation of our era. Recent discoveries in physics, biology, psychology and ecology have begun to restore status previously discredited spiritual visions of reality.

Carvajal (2013) believes that work spirituality has also become a significant aspect of organizational culture. For instance, Usman (2010) contends that the values of spirituality greatly enhance the sense of accomplishment in employees' which resultantly impacts on overall productivity and growth of the organizations. In this sense, spirituality then can be a factor that can intervene in all crucial aspects

of work life. The values of spirituality in today's work environment can be a great source of competitive advantage for any organization. In the same line, Wong (2003) strongly upheld that spiritual values like altruism, love, care, affection, and meaning creation lead to high organizational outcomes.

Based on the results of studies of Fry, Vituci, & Cedillo (2003), Townsend (1984), and Malone & Fry (2003), spirituality helps in enhancing the level of job satisfaction and fulfillment with an overall organizational accomplishment. They concluded that "both spiritual and God's values emphasize on love, care, innovation, affection, interconnectedness and better communication by creating an inner connection with work place that increases the levels of employees' job satisfaction and accomplishment which resultantly increases the overall organizational productivity."

Spirituality impacts on the strong communication and interpersonal relationship among employees by setting up a culture of individual support, collaboration and motivate the employees intrinsically that subsequently leads to highly productive and satisfied work force. Ryan & Grolnick (1986) and Ryan &

LaGuardia (2002) suggests that the organizations with cultures reflecting spiritual values, i.e. individual support, effective communication, coordination, collaboration and strong interpersonal relationship, motivates the employees' intrinsically by creating an inner happiness and satisfaction. Work spirituality is also a significant factor for maximizing employees' effectiveness, value and loyalty.

Sass (2000) believes that employees' effectiveness, reduced absenteeism, high growth and performance are the outcome of spiritual beliefs. Thus, spirituality would create an internal locus and cognitive attachment to remain loyal and careful for the future development of the organization. This is also the contention of Lilius, et al (2005) asserting that spirituality results in employees' cognitive and psychological association with their respective organizations that subsequently strengthens their commitment and devotion with a strong sense of fulfillment. This is made possible through a significant exchange of values that belongs to individuals and visionary values of organizations. In the analysis of Carvajal (2013), this refers to the coherence of organizational vision and mission and the employees' self fulfillment personified by a strong commitment and organizational accomplishment.

Work spirituality, then, enhances the skill development and work personalities of the organizational work force. This is the view of Tesser (1998) who posits that work spirituality develops knowledge, skills, abilities, talents, and creates a groomed personality of the employees at work which leads to the accomplishment of self-actualization and self-enrichment needs. The research of Burton and

O'Reilly (2002) further claims that the involvement of spiritual and religious values in ongoing managerial practices impart a significant impact on the overall organizational productivity. This implies that the values of spirituality are so averred for the organizational and individual accomplishment.

Spirituality has also influential connections with the human health and psychology. This was what Fry (2005) claimed that through ethical and moral up gradation the value of work spirituality are found beneficial in maintaining employees' health and psychological well-being. Similarly, Frew (2000) sustains that spirituality is found extremely beneficial in reducing the pressure, tension, anxiety and burden of work and makes the job more enjoyable.

Work spirituality has managerial significance and implications. Usman (2010) posited that there is a great importance of spirituality for managers and policy makers. He believes that the development of a spiritual culture in an organization will result to higher satisfaction among the employees of the organization as this helps the employees in creating an organizational perspective and meaning to match the individual's values and that of the organization. Carvajal (2013) believes that the more the involvement of spirituality in the organizational culture the more will be the sense of fulfillment in the employees, as a result they will be more effective in organizational accomplishment. In other words, it is the duty of the top level managers and HR managers to develop an orientation and training structure to enrich the work spirituality in newly hired as well as old and experienced employees for strategic performance of organizations.

B. On Spiritual Intelligence/Spiritual Quotient

Today, spiritual intelligence has also entered the world of scientific studies. Traditionally, Intelligence Quotient (IQ) is the sole gauge of human intelligence. And then there was Emotional Quotient (EQ). These two are usually used to measure a person's success in any endeavor.

Spiritual Intelligence (SI) or Spiritual Quotient (SQ) were introduced by Zohar and Marshall (2005) and maintained that it underpins IQ and EQ and makes success with fulfillment a reality. They define Spiritual intelligence as the "ability to access higher meanings, values, abiding purposes, and

unconscious aspects of the self and to embed these meanings, values, and purposes in living a richer and more creative life.”

Carvajal (2013) stresses that the development of spiritual intelligence leads to the development of spiritual capital that fundamentally reflects what an individual or an organization exists for, believes in, aspires to, and takes responsibility for. Thus, SI can play a significant role in the work place.

Covey (2004) describes spiritual intelligence as a key component of leadership and effectiveness when he observed that "spiritual intelligence is the central and most fundamental of all the intelligences, because it becomes the source of guidance.

In today's highly-technological world, secularism becomes inevitably a common tendency. People tend to lean more on the "worldly" – the "material" or "temporal" aspects of human existence as a gauge for happiness or success. The basic and most common understanding of "secular" today is anything that stands in opposition to the "religious" and the "spiritual." This means that something is secular when it can be categorized with the worldly, civil, non-religious sphere of human life. In other words, something is secular when it is not worshipped, when it is not venerated, and when it is open for critique, judgment, and replacement. Secularism is essentially characterized by the improvement of life by material means; that it is good to do good – whether there be other good or not, the good of the present life is good, and it is good to seek that good. For instance, secularism supports the individual against the pressure of the group and the individual conscience against the dogma of the group. Secularism is a variety of utilitarian social ethics that seeks human improvement without reference to religion and exclusively by means of human reason, science and social organization. In fact, in the moral sense, secularism is based on rational consideration regarding human well-being in this world, to the exclusion of considerations relating to God or the afterlife. This means that indifference to religion is presupposed, as religion is not seen as necessary or useful. In fact it is held suspect as the cause of much intolerance and even violence. In effect, secularism brings along with it individualism, relativism, materialism and agnosticism. Secularism can be considered as a result of postmodernism. Postmodernism is founded on the position that reality is not reflected in human understanding of it, but is rather constructed as the mind tries to understand its own personal reality. It is skeptical of explanations that claim to be valid for all groups, cultures, traditions, or races, and instead focuses on the relative truths of each person. In other words, in the postmodern understanding, interpretation is everything; reality only comes into being through our interpretations of what the world means to us individually. Fact is, there are no facts; there are only interpretations!

We are now in the spiritual intelligence revolution - a spontaneous movement in society and a significant new interest in the reality of spirit and its healing effects on life, health, community and well-being. In fact, recent discoveries in physics, biology, psychology and ecology, among others, have begun to restore status previously discredited spiritual visions of reality. Spiritual intelligence becomes a significant aspect of organizational culture. The values of spiritual intelligence could greatly enhance the sense of accomplishment in professionals which resultantly affects the overall productivity and growth of organizations. In this regard, spiritual intelligence can be a factor that can intervene in all crucial aspects of life. In other words, the values of spiritual intelligence in today's contemporary work environment can be a great source of competitive advantage for any organization. In addition, spiritual intelligence helps in enhancing the level of job satisfaction and fulfillment with an overall organizational accomplishment.

Some studies also reveal that "both spiritual and God's values emphasize on love, care, innovation, affection, interconnectedness and better communication by creating an inner connection that increases the levels of employees' job satisfaction and accomplishment which resultantly increases the overall organizational productivity." Spiritual intelligence impacts on the strong communication and interpersonal relationship among employees by setting up a culture of individual support, collaboration and motivate the employees intrinsically that subsequently leads to highly productive and satisfied work force. Thus, this posits that the organizations with cultures reflecting spiritual values, i.e. individual support, effective communication, coordination, collaboration and strong interpersonal relationship, motivates the employees' intrinsically by creating an inner happiness and satisfaction. It maximizes professionals effectiveness, value and loyalty.

Moreover, spiritual intelligence could enhance the skill development and work personalities of the organizational work force. It also may also develop knowledge, skills, abilities, talents, and creates a groomed personality of professionals at work that can lead to the accomplishment of self-actualization and self-enrichment needs.

Spiritual intelligence has also persuasive connections with the human health and psychology. Studies reveal that through ethical and moral dispositions, the value of spiritual intelligence is found beneficial in maintaining health and psychological well-being. Spiritual intelligence is found extremely beneficial in reducing the pressure, tension, anxiety and burden of work and makes the job more enjoyable.

Carvajal (2015) believes in his study that spiritual intelligence can have managerial implications. It is of great importance for managers and policy makers. The development of a spiritual culture will result to higher satisfaction among the professionals of organizations as this helps in creating an organizational perspective and meaning to match the individual's values and that of the organization. In other words, the more the involvement of spiritual intelligence in the organizational culture, the more will be the sense of fulfillment among professionals. As a result they will be more effective in organizational accomplishment.

The work morale of employees refers to the overall outlook, attitude, satisfaction, and confidence that employees feel at work. In fact, when employees are positive about their work environment and believe that they can meet their most important career and vocational needs, employee morale is positive or high (Heathfield, 2018). Some factors that have impact on employee morale include the effectiveness of managers or administrators, the quality of manager's or administrator's interaction with employees, and the way employees interact with each other and their spiritual dispositions on a day-to-day basis.

Horell (2014) study is entitled, "On Learning to See the World Religiously: Moral Awareness, Faith, and Public Moral Discourse." His study relates faith convictions with moral awareness. For him, "Morality is a constitutive dimension of Faith. Christians are called by God to show hospitality to the stranger, have a special concern for the poor and the oppressed, and respect the dignity of all persons as created in the image of God. He asserts that an openness to the guidance of God of the divine, the great religious traditions of the world can offer resources for forming and informing an understanding of the moral dimensions of life. He appeals that in guiding people to learn to see the world spiritually, one should help people to recognize and resist all forms of false humanism. He believes that such false understandings of the human person minimize the unique contributions that people of faith can make to public discussions of socio-moral issues as they draw insight from their distinctive faith perspectives. He further differentiates Secularism and secularization. In guiding people to learn to see the world religiously, religious educators should lead people to recognize the inadequacies of and to resist all forms of secularization. According to his study, this process of secularization "has been beneficial" because it enabled scientific enquiry, the arts, economic institutions, and other aspects of human activity to develop within their own social spheres. Moreover, because of the secularization of society public spaces were created for discussing social issues in which people stepped back from their specific life perspectives, including their commitments, in order to ensure that civil discourse was not plagued by destructive conflicts. However when the process of secularization is taken to the extreme, it fosters secularism. He describes secularism as the "ideological conviction that religion and belief in the spiritual and transcendent dimensions of life have no place in public life." Thus, from the perspective of secularism, faith convictions should be seen as purely private matters. He further contends that "secularism is problematic because it obscures from view the social dimensions of faith convictions and how insights grounded within our life context, including our rootedness in specific religious traditions and communities, contribute to our distinctive moral outlooks." In other words, in guiding people to see the world religiously, religious educators should encourage people to resist all forms of religious imperialism, that is, claims that moral outlook of one religious tradition is superior to other outlooks coupled with attempts to force this moral outlook on others.

Wigglesworth (2009) in his study, "Spiritual Intelligence and Why It Matters," defines spiritual intelligence as "the innate human need to connect with something larger than ourselves." This "something larger than ourselves" refers to something beyond our ego-self or constricted sense of self. It may be defined as having two components: the vertical components which include something sacred, divine, timeless and placeless...a Higher Power, Source, Ultimate Consciousness – or any other language the person prefers and desiring to be connected to and guided by this Source and the horizontal component which includes being of service to our fellow humans and to the planet at large. She defines Spiritual Intelligence as "the ability to behave with compassion and wisdom while maintaining inner and outer peace (equanimity) regardless of the circumstances." Compassion and wisdom together form the manifestation of Love. "Behave" is important because it focuses on how well we maintain our center, stay calm, and actually treat others with compassion and wisdom. The statement of "regardless of the circumstances" shows that we can maintain our peaceful center and loving behaviors even under great

stress. Based on this definition she created a list of skills which she believes represent the skills of Spiritual Intelligence. These skills were categorized in four domains namely: First, the higher self/ego self awareness, which includes awareness of own world, awareness of life purpose (mission), awareness of values hierarchy, awareness of Ego self / Higher Self and complexity of inner thought; second, the universal awareness, which includes awareness of interconnectedness of all life, awareness of worldviews of others, breadth of time / space perception, awareness of limitations/power of human perception, awareness of Spiritual laws, and experience of transcendent oneness; third, the higher self/ego self mastery which includes commitment to spiritual growth, keeping higher self in charge, living your purpose and values, sustaining your faith, and seeking guidance from Spirit; and lastly, the social mastery / spiritual presence which includes, a wise and effective spiritual teacher/mentor, a wise and effective change agent, makes compassionate and wise decisions, a calming, healing presence, and being aligned with the ebb and flow of life. Furthermore, she explains that each of these skills has been described in five levels of skill proficiency. Level 1 is when a person is able to communicate understanding of the nature of Ego self- including its origin and the purpose it serves in spiritual development; level 2 when one demonstrates ability to observe personal Ego in operation and comment on what seems to trigger Ego eruptions; level 3 when he/she demonstrates awareness of and ability to periodically "listen to" Spirit or Higher Self as a separate voice from Ego self; level 4 when one hears the voice of Spirit or Higher Self clearly and understands the "multiple voices" that Ego self can give authority to voice of Higher Self in important decisions, and level 5 when the Spirit or Higher Self voice is clear and consistent. Ego self is present and is a joyful advisor to Higher Self. There is no longer a struggle between the two voices. Rather there is a sense of only "one voice" ...the Higher Self (Authentic Self, Spirit) voice

Finally, she believes that the development of SQ will not only benefit individuals, it will also benefit their families, communities, and the companies they work for. This leads to a meaningful work, improved products and services, and ensuring responsible corporate behavior.

King (2010) article entitled "A Viable Model of Spiritual Intelligence" presents the following model for spiritual intelligence:

In this model, **spiritual intelligence** is defined as a set of mental capacities which contribute to the awareness, integration, and adaptive application of the nonmaterial and transcendent aspects of one's existence, leading to such outcomes as deep existential reflection, enhancement of meaning, recognition of a transcendent self, and mastery of spiritual states. To elaborate further, the following are the meanings of the concepts presented in this model:

Critical Existential Thinking: the capacity to critically contemplate meaning, purpose, and other existential/metaphysical issues (e.g., existence, reality, death, the universe); to come to original existential conclusions or philosophies; and to contemplate non-existential issues in relation to one's existence (i.e., from an existential perspective).

Personal Meaning Production: the ability to derive personal meaning and purpose from all physical & mental experiences, including the capacity to create and master (i.e., live according to) a life purpose.

Transcendental Awareness: the capacity to identify transcendent dimensions/patterns of the self (i.e., a transpersonal or transcendent self), of others, and of the physical world (e.g., holism, nonmaterialism) during normal states of consciousness, accompanied by the capacity to identify their relationship to one's self and to the physical world.

Conscious State Expansion: the ability to enter and exit higher/spiritual states of consciousness (e.g. pure consciousness, cosmic consciousness, unity, oneness) at one's own discretion (as in deep contemplation or reflection, meditation, prayer, etc.).

According to him, this model proves that Spiritual intelligence performs quite well according to traditional criteria for intelligence. This model satisfies the primary criterion: spiritual intelligence represents a set of mental abilities, as opposed to behaviors or experiences.

C. On Some Key Concepts in Crafting Project-based Activities in relation to Si and WM

According to Kulshrestha & Singhal (2017) spirituality intelligence is considered one of the key factors for the success of the educational institutions and ultimately for the professional life of the teachers. In the present preview of modernization the quality of being spiritually intelligent is necessary for the teachers too. They emphasize that teacher must have high spiritual intelligence which will be the highest guidance to them to carry out their functions as teachers with the highest regards and as noble as possible. The major role of a holistic educator is to awaken creativity and spiritual intelligence of learners (Colalillo Kates, 2002). Thus, it is important to make teachers spiritually intelligent as they can then enlighten and guide future educational reforms and policies in relation to both contents and methods for the holistic development of the individuals. Spiritual intelligence enables the teachers to have the ability to create meaning based on deep understanding and the positive attitude to solve problems. They are generally well satisfied with their workplace. Vaughan (2002) gave three components of spiritual intelligence, namely, the ability to create meaning based on deep understanding of existential questions, an awareness of and the ability to use multiple levels of consciousness in problem solving, an awareness of the interconnection of all beings to each other and to the transcendent. The major factor associated with school teacher's decision to leave or to remain in the teaching profession is their job satisfaction because job satisfaction is related to working conditions and level of professionalism as a key factor in successfully recruiting and retaining teachers (Stanbury & Zimmerman, 2000). Shahnawaz & Jafri, 2009 believe that job Satisfaction is "a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job and an attitude toward one's job. In other words, teacher's job satisfaction refers to a teacher's affective relation to his or her teaching role and is the function of the perceived relationship between what one wants from teaching and what one perceives it is offering to a teacher (Zembylas & Papanastasiou, 2004). Dincer (2009) mentioned that spiritual intelligence provides a sense of personal wholeness, goal and direction, He claimed that teachers with high level of spiritual intelligence were able to mold students from all age groups to experience a wholesome life filled with self-respect and creativity. Teachers with spiritual intelligence are more satisfied with their jobs and spiritual Intelligence has positive influence on job satisfaction (Cherati, Mahdavi, & Rezacian, 2013).

In her study, Vas (2017) that the application of SI in practical day-to-day life affects the family life. She believes that the culture of family life can easily revolve around too much 'familiarity'. This results in behaviors which can swing from rejection, resistance and avoidance one moment, to attachment, dependency and clinginess the next. Being spiritually intelligent in a family context allows individuals to find a more mature way to relate, free of emotional dependency, and able to embrace 'the other' regardless of their behavior or their emotional state.

SI also affects working life. According to her, when spiritual intelligence is brought into the workplace work ceases to become a daily chore, and becomes a creative process of service and contribution. Others are seen and treated as people and not objects/resources to get a job done, and individuals have an opportunity to learn the inner, invisible and subtle skills of building and sustaining relationships in any area of life.

Moreover, Vas (2017) in her study mentioned some benefits of enhanced SI, namely: Spiritual intelligence enables one to have more balanced life; helps one to effectively manage and control one's emotions; helps one to become more reflective and introspective; helps to build capacity to face suffering and life's ups and downs; empowers one to challenge the status quo and think outside the box; and reluctance to cause unnecessary harm to others

As a result of her study, she recommends some activities that can foster spiritual intelligence in the workplace namely; the Employee Assistance Programs (EAP) because employees must be assisted in all spheres of their life like employee counselling and personality reengineering in order to shape the core values, beliefs, and assumptions and eventually basic thinking patterns can be beneficial; servant leadership that plays a critical role while creating any culture because servant leadership is more effective in building morale, trust, commitment, and job satisfaction which eventually build as spiritual work culture; Diversity Programs because diversity practices create a work environment or culture that allows

everyone to contribute to the organization and diversity at workplace can be created through discouraging formation of groups on the basis of religion, caste, gender or race and people should respect diversity in organizations – an inclusive culture and every individual including minority and women feel one with the culture; work-life balance programs because today, workers have many responsibilities such as work, children, housework, volunteering, and caring for spouse and elderly parents, which leads to stress on individuals, families and the communities in which they reside and this is to avoid work-life conflict as this is a serious problem that impacts workers, their employers and communities.

D. On related studies conducted on Spiritual intelligence, Spiritual Intelligence and Work Morale

The preliminary study of Olarte, Gamboa, and Buyacco (2016) tried to determine the level of spiritual intelligence of SMU employees. This study utilizes a standardized test. The work spiritual intelligence of the respondents was subjected to the scoring guidelines and interpretation provided by the proponent of the tool. The items in the tool are thematic, that is, they speak of the three connections in spiritual intelligence, namely: (1) Connection to the self; (2) Connection to others; and, (3) Connection to a “greater being.” These three determine the spiritual intelligence of individuals. The results of their study show that in the three connections mentioned above, the respondents have high spiritual intelligence. This is shown by the high level of agreement to the most of the items mentioned in the tool. Out of the items in the tool, two are on top rank being rated with high level of agreement. Respondents show high level of agreement on items related to the Transcendent, the Divine, or God.

The study of Rani, Abidin, and Hamid (2013) entitled “The Impact of Spiritual Intelligence on Work Performance: Case studies in Government Hospitals of East Coast of Malaysia” reveals that there are positive correlation found between spiritual intelligence and work performance. The results show that nurses with higher spiritual intelligence perform more in their work. Spiritual intelligence is related with health, leadership, and it influences work performance. There was a positive relationship between Spiritual intelligence and work performance. In other word, when nurses apply Spiritual intelligence in work, their performance increase. The significant value from the Spiritual intelligence construct to work performance construct suggested that the Spiritual intelligence should be applied by the nurses and should be implement in the planning policies and training in government hospitals.

Hall and Edwards’ (2014) article “The Spiritual Assessment Inventory: A Theistic Model and Measure for Assessing Spiritual Development” introduces the Spiritual Assessment Inventory (SAI), a relationally-based measure designed to assess two dimensions of spiritual development: Awareness of God and Quality of Relationship with God. Their study presents exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses of SAI. They also discuss and suggest future research and implications for clinical use of the instrument. Thus, the SAI may be instrumental in the process of study of the present research. This study also helps in the construction of survey questionnaire particularly on spiritual assessment.

The study of Carvajal (2014) entitled ‘Spiritualizing Services In The Government ‘ The Effects Of Spiritual intelligence On The Work Of Selected Philippine Government Employees contends that Spiritual Intelligence or Spiritual Quotient (SQ) provides the meaning for one’s existence, aims and success. It is considered higher than Intelligence Quotient (IQ) and Emotional Quotient (EQ). It is more than just a connection to the divine. SQ is a connection to self, others, and the transcendent. His study explored the spiritual intelligence at work of selected Philippine government employees, as well as the importance and effects of their spiritual intelligence in their work. Utilizing a multi-method research design, one hundred government employees were purposively sampled to answer a survey-questionnaire, and a standardized SQ test. The study found that the government employees have a fair connection to their self and are fairly good at relationship building. Though they value their connection to the transcendent and have a desire to deepen this relationship, this is not however a part of their daily awareness. The respondents indicated that spiritual intelligence is important in public service and strongly agree that spiritual intelligence in the public service promotes honesty, patience, integrity at work, good relationships with clients and customers, good working relationships with co-workers, superiors and subordinates, and creates meaning of their work as a vocation.

The dissertation of Burgula (2014) entitled ‘Contemporary issues, Perceived Needs and Spiritual Maturity of Christian Students in basic educations in Hyderabad in 2006 focusing on an assessment of the perceived needs and spiritual maturity of Christian students in basic educations in Hyderabad provided some ideas on how to conduct FGD. His exploratory research tried to identify the level of spiritual

maturity on Christian students in basic educations in Hyderabad, India. His study presents the implications of the findings that will help the researchers. His research becomes vital in developing a curriculum that may help address the important issues and needs of basic education students in order to facilitate an atmosphere where spiritual growth and maturity can take place.

The study of Gamboa, et. al., (2019) revealed that generally, SMU employees have relatively high level of spiritual intelligence and work morale. However, noticeably, considering all the items in the survey, the highest rated items were on "HIGH EXTENT" and "USUALLY" as well as the lowest were "LOW EXTENT" and "SOMETIMES." This implies that their SI and WM can still be improved and be made higher. Note that no single item was rated to a "very high extent" and "always." In other words, there is a big room for further improvement on their spiritual and work dispositions.

Their study also revealed that Marian employees remain steadfast in their connection with God, their relationship with others and themselves. Consciously or unconsciously, their spiritual intelligence is basically profound and their religious inclinations remain active and strong. This is testified by their enthusiasm and active participation in religious and spiritual activities in school. The call to holiness by Pope Francis is well responded to by the employees of SMU. This is testified by their responses in the survey. Their holiness is well expressed and reflected in their jobs assigned to them.

Results of their study showed that the work morale of SMU employees was relatively high, though it can still be improved. Despite the challenges of the times, SMU employees proved their commitment and dedication as well as their loyalty and love to the institution as testified by the results of this study. One can even conclude that the full-time permanent academic and non-academic personnel are happy and fulfilled in their own workplaces and in their own job assignments.

This study proved that spiritual intelligence plays a vital role in the work morale of employees. There is indeed a significant relevance and connection of spiritual intelligence and the work morale of employees. In short, employees become more fulfilled in their workplaces if they are spiritual intelligence nourished.

Their study was not exhaustive, perhaps not even strictly conclusive. The findings, discussions, perceptions, opinions, and conjectures remain wanting, more so tentative. In this case, here are some of their recommendations included first, to better enhance the religious and spiritual activities given to employees such as recollections, Eucharistic celebrations, praise and worship activities, and the like; second, greater attention must be rendered to non-academic employees to boost their spiritual intelligence and their work morale and the administration must ensure that non-academic personnel will not be left behind and provide more opportunities that will help them feel that they are not simply "support system" in the institution but part and parcel of the whole organization; third, policies concerning academic and non-academic personnel should be reviewed and analyzed regularly to see the relevance of its provisions and most importantly, enhance an open communication and information between employees and administrators to ensure trust and healthy exchange of opinions on matters concerning work. Administration needs to listen more intently to the voice of the employees; fourth, bring back the listening heart of the institution to the employees by avoiding too much legalism and ensure corporate trust; fifth, there should be more serious activities and concrete and clear programs for employees that will directly involve them especially in institutional decision-making; and lastly, for future studies, the survey could be conducted to the basic education departments as they may differ in some aspects like philosophical worldview, spiritual intelligence, work circumstances, and perceptions in the personal, relational and spiritual dimensions. This will strengthen further the findings and claims of this study.

Synthesis

Based on the literatures and studies of authors and researchers, spiritual intelligence plays a vital role in the life of individuals. SI or SQ reveals some scientific evidences regarding its role in the multi intelligences and skills of a person. As revealed in the studies cited above, SI has a connection to the work morale of employees. Spiritual intelligence affects the performance of people in their work places. SI includes different aspects or dimensions of human life especially in the work place. Spiritual intelligence therefore becomes a major part of the work morale of people, particularly those engaged in various professional works in different work environments.

XIII. Methodology

Research Design

This study will use a multi-method quantitative and qualitative, descriptive-comparative and correlational research design that uses a research-modified and contextualized spiritual intelligence survey tool based on standardized questionnaire and a work morale survey tool. It will also use open-ended questions to reinforce the statistical results. It will use population method for the respondents.

For the quantitative method, descriptive statistics shall be used through the computations of the mean scores to determine the level of SI and WM of the respondents. The qualitative data shall be taken from the answers to open-ended questions which will be incorporated the survey questionnaires. The statistical computation tool to be used for the comparative and correlational aspects shall be determined based on the normality of the distribution of the respondents (as to whether para-metric or non-parametric).

Research Environment

This stage of the study will be conducted at St. Mary's University, Basic education Department. Recently, some basic education teachers and office personnel decided to resign and some are now employed in public schools and state universities. In short, this specific workplace is seemingly fitted to conduct the current study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are all the full-time permanent employees of Saint Mary's University, both the teaching and non-teaching personnel in the Basic Education department.

The Sources of data

The main sources of data will be the result of survey on the level of SI and the level of work morale as well as the answers to open-ended questions.

The Research Instruments

The following instruments will be used in this study after a conduct of pilot-testing that will eventually test their statistical validity and reliability.

1. SI Survey Questionnaire. A modified and contextualized survey questionnaire will be used by the researchers to measure the level of SI of the respondents. The SI questionnaire is based on the tools used by Carvajal (2011) on spiritual intelligence among selected government employees and Carvajal (2013) on spiritual intelligence among high performing teachers. This tool was also based on the concepts of Zohar and Marshall (2000) on spiritual quotient. Seemingly similar SI questionnaire is provided by King (2008) Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory (SISRI) which includes scoring procedures, validation and reliability testing.
2. WM Survey Questionnaire A modified and contextualized standard survey questionnaire used by the researchers to measure the level of WM of the respondents. This is based on the tools used by the National Research Business Institute on Employee Engagement Survey (2018) and Zarca Interactive (2018) on Employee Morale Survey.
3. Open-ended questions will be imbedded in the questionnaires to reinforce the quantitative data..

The Data Gathering Procedure

The survey for SI and WM shall be conducted after establishing its statistical validity and reliability. The survey questionnaire shall be distributed to the identified respondents from both basic education teaching and non-teaching employees. The questionnaires will be gathered by the researchers after the respondents are given considerable time to finish answering. Encoding follows as soon as the questionnaires are retrieved for statistical computation and transcriptions of qualitative data from answers to open-ended questions included in the tools.

The Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

The survey shall be subjected to a computation through the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software 16.0. Qualitative data gathered from the answers to open-ended questions shall be thematically summarized and analyzed vis-à-vis the result of the survey which will be utilized to triangulate the results of the quantitative survey.

For the SI survey, the scale to be used for interpretation is the degree of extent as indicated below:

- VLE:** to a very low extent **(1.0-1.49)**
- LE** to a low extent **(1.5-2.49),**
- AVE:** to an average extent **(2.5-3.49)**
- VHE:** to a high extent **(3.5-4.0)**

For the WM survey, the scale to be used for the interpretation is indicated below. They will write the corresponding number of points to every item in the questionnaire.

- Always = 4 points – **(3.5-4.0)** high work morale (HWM)
- Usually = 3 points – **(2.5-3.49)** Moderate (MWM)
- Sometimes = 2 points – **(1.5-2.49)** Low (LWM)
- Rarely = 1 points - **(1.0-1.49)** (Very Low (VLWM))

For the interpretation and correlation between the SI and WM, the items in SI will be classified thematically as to connection to oneself, others, and the transcendence. The items or each item may be correlated to the items in the WM thematically. The findings on levels of SI and the WM will be analyzed and to determine their correlations. The results of both survey will also be compared to the variables indicated in this study. Finally, the results of this study will be a possible basis for policy recommendations to enhance SI and WM for basic education employees.

For the descriptive statistics and the correlational and comparative computations, the statistical tools to be used shall be determined by the normality of the distribution of respondents (parametric or non-parametric).

XIV. References

- Bowell, R. A. (2004). *Spiritual intelligence: The practical pursuit of purpose, success and happiness*. London: Nicholas Brealey Publishing.
- Bruce, W.M. (2000). Public administrator attitudes about spiritual intelligence: An exploratory study. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 30, 460-472.
- Bryant, A. N. (2007). Gender differences in spiritual development during the basic education years. *Sex Roles*, 56(11-12), 835–846. doi: 10.1007/s11199-007-9240-2.
- Burton, M. & O'Reilly, C. (2000). *The impact of high commitment values and practices on technology*.
- Carvajal, A& Ramos, C. (2013). *The spiritual intelligence of teaching: The work spiritual intelligence of selected high performance teachers in Catholic Grade Schools*.
- Carvajal, A.L.P. (2011). Spiritualizing public service: The effects of spiritual intelligence in the work of Philippine government employees. *SPUQC Journal* 4, 23-64.
- Carvajal, A.L.P. (2011). Spiritualizing public service: The effects of spirituality in the work of Philippine *Communication Studies*, 51, 195–207.
- Cherati, h., Mahdavi, I., & Rezacian, J. (2013). The mediating role of job satisfaction between Spiritual Intelligence and Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Research in Organizational Behavior and Human Resource Management*, 1 (1), 1-11.
- Colalillo, K. I. (2002). *Awakening creativity and spiritual intelligence: the soul work of holistic educators* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Company Success 500. (2018) Employee Morale survey. Retrieved September 25, 2019 from http://www.companysuccess500.com/employee_morale/Employee%20Morale%20Survey.pdf
<https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/employee-surveys/>
- Covey, S. (2004). *The 8th Habit: From Effectiveness to Greatness*. USA: Simon and Schuster.
- Cunha, M., Rego, A., & D'Oliveria, T. (2011). Management ideologies and organizational spiritual intelligence: A typology. Retrieved June 26, 2011 from <http://ideas.repec.org/p/unl/unlfep/wp452.html>
- Finley, M. (1999). Dana Zohar on rewiring the biological and organizational brain. Retrieved October 1, 2019 http://mfinley.com/experts/zohar/Zohar_Precis.htm
- Fry, L. (2005). Toward a theory of ethical and spiritual well-being and corporate social responsibility through spiritual leadership. In R.A. Giacalone, & C.L. Jurkiewicz (Eds). *Positive psychology in business ethics and corporate responsibility*. Greenwich, CT: Information Age Publishing.
- Fry, L. (2005). Toward a theory of ethical and spiritual well-being and corporate social responsibility
- Fry, L. W., Vitucci, S. & Cedillo, M. (2003). *Transforming the army through spiritual leadership*.
-

- Giacalone, & C. L. Jurkiewicz (Eds.), *Handbook of workplace spirituality and organizational performance*. New York: M. E. Sharp.
- Giacalone, R. A. & Jurkiewicz, C. L. (2003). *Toward a science of workplace spirituality*. In R. A. Goleman, D. (2006). *Emotional Intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. 10th Anniversary Ed. USA: Bantam.
- Goleman, D. (2006). *Emotional Intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. (10th). USA: Bantam. government employees. *SPUQC Journal* 4, 23-64.
- Ker-Dincer, M. (2007). Educators' role as spiritually intelligent leaders in educational institutions. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 4(1).
- King, D. (2008). *A Viable Model of Spiritual Intelligence*. Retrieved July 2018 from <http://www.davidbking.net/spiritualintelligence/sisri.htm>.
- Kumar, D. (2011) *Spiritual intelligence, productivity and effective management: Transforming a business*. Retrieved June 26, 2011 from <http://ideas.repec.org/p/wpa/wuwpdc/0508003.html>
- Kumar, D. (2011) *Spirituality, productivity and effective management: Transforming a business*. PLC Publishing
- Malone, P. & Fry, L. W. (2003). *Transforming schools through spiritual leadership*. PLC Publishing.
- Miller, W. C. (2001). Responsible Leadership: Base Your Leadership on Spiritual Roots. *Executive Excellence*, 18, 5-27.
- Mitroff, I. & Denton, E. (1999). A study of spiritual intelligence in the workplace. *Sloan Management Review*, 40, 83-92.
- National Research Business Institute. (2016). *Employee Engagement Survey Sample*. Retrieved July 2018 from <https://www.nbrii.com/employee-survey-questions-template/>.
- Neal, J. (2004). *Spiritual intelligence at work self-assessment*. Retrieved June 28, 2011 from <http://www.spiritatwork.org/>.
- Olarte, B., Gamboa, H., Buyacco, B. (2018). *Spiritual intelligence in the Workplace: The Work Spiritual intelligence of SMU Employees*. SMU Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 1. *organizations*. Retrieved June 26, 2011 from <http://ideas.repec.org/a/kap/jbuset/v66y2006i4p357-375.html>.
- Palmer, P. (2003). Reflections on Spiritual intelligence in Teacher Education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 54, 376-385.
- Palmer, P. (2011) *Teaching as a Spiritual Practice*. Retrieved August 28, 2015 from <http://www.spiritualintelligenceandpractice.com/blogs/maps.php?id=16445> perspective on basic psychological needs across the life span. In S. Qualls, & R. Ables (Eds.), *Dialogues on psychology and aging* (145–172). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association. *Public Administration Review*, 67, (1), 88-102.
- Rani, A, Abidin, I., and Hamid, M. R. (2013) *The Impact of Spiritual Intelligence on Work Performance: Case studies in Government Hospitals of East Coast of Malaysia*. Retrieved July 2018 from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.426.6264&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Rani, A.A. Abidin, I., and Ab Hamid, M. R. (2013). *The Macrotheme Review* 2(3). Retrieved October 1, 2019 from http://mfinley.com/experts/zohar/Zohar_Precis.htm Retrieved September 26, 2019 from <http://ideas.repec.org/p/wpa/wuwpdc/0508003.html>
- Ryan, K. D. & Grolnick, W. S. (1986). Origins and pawns in the classroom: Self-report and projective
- Ryan, K. D. & La Guardia, J. G. (2000). What is being optimized over development? A self-determination theory
- Sass, J. S. (2000). Characterizing organizational spiritual intelligence: An organizational communication culture approach. *Communication studies*, 51, 195–207.
- Sass, J. S. (2000). Characterizing organizational spirituality: An organizational communication culture approach. *Satisfaction. International Business Research*, 3, (2), 10-12.
- Shahnawaz, M. G., & Jafri, M. H. (2009). Job attitudes as predictor of employee turnover among stayers and leavers/hoppers. *Journal of Management Research*, 9(3), 159.
- Sheep, M. (2011). *Nurturing the whole person: The ethics of workplace spirituality in a society*.
- Smith, J. & Malcolm, A. (2010). *Spirituality, leadership and values in the NHS*.
- Spiritual Capital (2007). Retrieved June 26, 2011 from www.alchemylab.com
- Spiritual Capital (2012). Retrieved June 27, 2013 from <http://danahzohar.com/www2/?p=641>

- start-ups*. Unpublished masteral thesis, Sloan School of Management, M.I.T, Cambridge.
- Stansbury, K., & Zimmerman, J. (2000). *Lifelines to the classroom: designing support for beginning teachers*. knowledge brief.
- Tacey, D. (2004). *The spiritual intelligence revolution: The emergence of contemporary spiritual intelligence*. Routledge: New York.
- Tacey, D. (2004). *The spirituality revolution: The emergence of contemporary spirituality*. Routledge: New York.
- Tesser, A.(1988). Toward a self-evaluation maintenance model of social behavior. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *The American Review of Public Administration*, 30, 460-472.
- Usman, A. (2010). Spiritual Consciousness in Banking Managers and its Impact on Job Satisfaction. *International Business Research*, 3, 2, 10-12.
- Vas, E. (2017). Spiritual Intelligence: A Secret Key to Employee Engagement. *International Journal of Engineering Technology Science and Research*, 4, (10), 441-449.
- Vaughan, F. (2002) What is Spiritual Intelligence? *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 42, 2., 16-33.
- Wigglesworth, C. (2018). Spiritual Intelligence and Why It Matters. Retrieved July 2018 from <http://www.innerworkspublishing.com/news/vol22/intelligence.htm>
- Wolman, R. (2001). *Thinking with your soul. Spiritual intelligence and why it matters*. USA: Harmony Books.
- Wong, P. T. P. (2003). Spiritual intelligence and meaning at work. Retrieved September 17, 2019 from http://www.meaning.ca/articles/presidents_column/print_copy/spiritual_intelligence_work
- Zembylas, M., & Papanastasiou, E. (2004). Job satisfaction among school teachers in Cyprus. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 42(3), 357-374.
- Zarca Interactive (2018). Employee Morale Survey. Retrieved July 2018 from <http://www.zarca.com/Online-Survey-Resource/Sample-Surveys/employee-satisfaction-survey-detailed-version.pdf>
- Zohar, D. & Marshall, I. (2000). *SQ - spiritual intelligence: The ultimate intelligence*. USA: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC.
- Zohar, D. & Marshall, I. (2005). *Spiritual capital: Wealth we can live by*. USA: Bloomsbury
- Zohar, D. (1997). *Rewiring the corporate brain: Using the new science to rethink how we structure and lead organization*. USA: Berret- Koehler.

XV. Project Timetable

Month	Activity
August to September	Finalization of Chapters 1-3, Survey Tools
October	Data Gathering
November	Encoding of Data
December	Submission of Raw Data for Statistical computation
January-February	Data interpretation
March- April	Presentation and submission of Final Copy

XVI. Research Tools

Survey Questionnaire

Dear Respondents:

Greetings! Pax Christi!

This is a questionnaire which aims to measure an employee's spiritual intelligence [*Your connectedness to self and others through relationships; deriving meaning, purpose, and direction in life; and openness to exploring a relationship with a higher power or powers that transcend human existence and human knowing.*] (Part I) and the level of Work Morale (Part II). Please take time to read the following and eventually rate each item according to your own **honest perception**. Thank you for your time and cooperation for this endeavor. The results of this study will provide basis for institutional policy recommendation or programs to enhance the work morale of employees.

Yours truly,

Henry Gamboa, Liberty Rosario, PhD and Benito Buyacco, Jr.
The Researchers

I. Profile

A. Name _____ (optional)

B. Gender male female (*please check*)

C. Work Assignment

- Teaching
- Non-Teaching

C. Years of Service _____

Please answer **honestly** the following questions by rating them using the scale below. Put a **CHECK MARK** on your corresponding answers.

- VLE:** very low extent (1)
- LE** low extent (2),
- HE:** high extent (3)
- VHE:** very high extent (4)

PART I. Spiritual Intelligence Survey

Personal Dimension	VLE (1)	LE (2)	HE (3)	VHE (4)
1. I am very aware of my values and beliefs at work.				
2. In difficult situations, I find that a calm part of me can remain detached and observe my thoughts, feelings and behaviors.				
3. I do not feel the need to grow or develop myself at work.				
4. If I found myself in a work situation where I was asked to compromise my values, I would have to stick to my values, even if it hurt me or my career.				
5. I have a real sense of calling about the work I do.				
6. My mission in life is very clear to me.				
7. I am very aware of my values and beliefs at work.				
8. In difficult situations, I find that a calm part of me can remain detached				

and observe my thoughts, feelings and behaviors.				
9. I do not feel the need to grow or develop myself at work.				
10. If I found myself in a work situation where I was asked to compromise my values, I would have to stick to my values, even if it hurt me or my career.				

Relational Dimension				
11. It is important to accept that others in my workplace may not have the same values and beliefs that I do.	VLE (1)	LE (2)	HE (3)	VHE (4)
12. People I work with describe me as calm and non-judgmental.				
13. When someone has done something that makes me angry, I find it very difficult to forgive them.				
14. I have a great deal of compassion for the leaders of my organization.				
15. It is important to keep business life and personal life separate in my relationships at work.				
16. I often feel a real sense of love and caring for the people I interact with at work.				
17. My primary motivation at work is to be of service to others.				
18. I am deeply concerned about the effects of some business practices on the planet.				
19. The reality of business is that sometimes you just have to compromise your values for the sake of the company or for your career.				
20. Dealing with people at work is a great cause of frustration for me.				

Spiritual Dimension				
21. I have had one or more transcendent experiences that have affected the way I feel about my work.	VLE (1)	LE (2)	HE (3)	VHE (4)
22. I try to have daily contact with my Higher Power, the Divine, God, or Universal Consciousness.				
23. When I need special help or guidance in my work, I turn to prayer, meditation, or other spiritual guidance.				
24. I feel divinely guided to the work I am doing.				
25. I have a regular spiritual or religious practice that I find helpful to me in my work.				
26. I believe that my work is part of a larger divinely guided plan.				
27. I feel a sense of the sacred in my workplace.				
28. Because of my belief in something greater than myself, I try to live in alignment with key virtues such as trustworthiness, humility, justice, and unity.				
29. I have had one or more transcendent experiences that have affected the way I feel about my work.				
30. I try to have daily contact with my Higher Power, the Divine, God, or Universal Consciousness.				

Part II. Employee Work Morale. This assessment tool reveals your employee work morale based on “work environment” and “employee engagement.” Please answer in full honesty. Please mark your response to each of the questions below

- Always = 4 points
- Usually = 3 points
- Sometimes = 2 points
- Rarely = 1 points

___ 1. I feel as part of "the SMU family"

___ 2. I am treated more as a partner/team member than as an employee.

Is "feeling as if you belong to a work team/work family" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or NO (Please encircle)

___ 3. Information is openly shared between administrators and employees.

___ 4. Administrators give all of the information I need to perform my job tasks.

Is "having an open line of communication with management" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 5. At SMU, we are rewarded for our performance and striving to achieve excellence.

___ 6. My administrators recognize the extra effort and actions that I do to perform the best job at SMU.

Is "being recognized and rewarded by management" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 7. My opinion is listened to by administrators when making decisions that involve my work tasks.

___ 8. I am involved in SMU extra curricular activities such as sporting teams, etc.

Is "being involved in decision making" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale.

Yes or No

___ 9. I find my work interesting and fulfilling at SMU.

___ 10. I feel like a contributor to SMU success.

Is "being enthusiastic about your job" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale.

Yes or No

___ 11. SMU provides plenty of opportunities for personal growth.

___ 12. SMU provides technical training so that I can advance in my career.

Is "being provided with advancement opportunities" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 13. At my department, the motivation level is moderate to high on a daily basis.

___ 14. My work gives me a feeling of personal accomplishment.

Is "feeling motivated" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 15. I am dedicated to improve my performance every day.

___ 16. I am devoted to the work tasks assigned.

Is "being committed to work" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 17. I am proud of being a Marian employee.

___ 18. I would like to grow and achieve my career goals within SMU.

Is "being loyal to SMU" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 19. I believe SMU has high level of ethics and spiritual intelligence.

___ 20. I trust top management integrity.

Is "being able to trust management" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 21. My administrators always listen to my suggestions.

___ 22. My administrators always show appreciation for every extra effort I put in my work.

Is "being appreciated by your supervisor" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 23. My administrators give me enough opportunities to take an active role as a leader.

___ 24. My job gives me enough opportunities and independence to use my skills and abilities to make my own decisions.

Is "being empowered to make your own decisions" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 25. People within my group or department cooperate with each other rather than compete.

___ 26. My administrators encourage teamwork and cooperation to achieve targeted goals.

Is "working in teams" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 27. I am satisfied with my wages.

___ 28. I would prefer working based on performance than by hourly or salary rates.

Is "being compensated" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 29. My employer provides plenty resources and training opportunities.

___ 30. SMU facilitates ongoing training to upgrade my skills

Is "being provided with training opportunities" an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 31. I feel comfortable talking to my administrators whenever there is a problem.

___ 32. I like knowing my supervisor's point of view whenever I have to make an important decision.

Is “feeling comfortable consulting your supervisor” an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 33. Policies and procedures are explained adequately within SMU.

___ 34. Work policies are fair at SMU.

Are “fair company policies & guidelines” an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

___ 35. My personal and spiritual values are similar to SMU values.

___ 36. Organizational values such as spiritual intelligence, honesty, integrity, and ethics are observed at SMU.

Are “values such as spiritual intelligence, ethics and integrity” an important factor for you to achieve High Employee Morale?

Yes or No

Do you think spiritual intelligence affects the work morale of an employee? Why or why not?

What are some of the challenges or problems you encountered that you consider as hindrances to a healthy work morale in your workplace? Why?

XVII. Signatories

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